

Modeling megawatt-scale hydrogen electrolysis plants with frequency support capability

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ABSTRACT

With the growing integration of intermittent renewable energy, hydrogen electrolyzers (HEs) are emerging as vital power-to-gas assets. However, utilizing these systems for ancillary services like Frequency Sensitive Mode (FSM) and Virtual Synchronous Mechanism (VSM) impacts their internal dynamics, a topic that remains underexplored. To analyze these interactions, this study develops a hybrid dynamical modeling framework and assesses its performance under FSM/VSM operation through a MW-scale case study. This framework integrates lumped HE electrolyzer models with first-order dynamic approximations of the peripheral balance-of-plant (BoP) components. The HE model accurately emulates the 17.5 MW Siemens Silyzer 300, successfully reproducing manufacturer polarization curves and transient responses. Findings highlight that the Silyzer 300 cells operate within a current density range of 0.16 to 2.5 A/cm², yielding stack efficiencies between 76.32% and 99.71% and cell voltages from 1.49 to 1.94 V. While maximum efficiency occurs at 80 °C and 1 bar, the electrolyzer demonstrates similar efficiencies at current densities below 0.5 A/cm², regardless of the temperature. To evaluate its performance within a 1000 MW wind farm scenario, the HE plant was scaled to a 507 MW capacity, comprising 29 Silyzer 300 modules. The study further quantifies the inherent trade-off between grid stabilization and production consistency. Although FSM and VSM activation effectively mitigates frequency and voltage deviations, it induces fluctuations in hydrogen output and thermal stress, particularly when stack efficiencies drop below 85%. Furthermore, the sensitivity analysis highlights the critical role of BoP dynamics in determining the suitability of HEs for FSM applications. While this suitability depends on installation's intrinsic characteristics, results show that slow HE BoP dynamics offer limited frequency support during fast frequency transients. Ultimately, the proposed hybrid framework serves as a robust approach, offering a predictive tool for operators to optimize large-scale hydrogen production while maintaining grid resilience.

1. Introduction

A hydrogen electrolyzer (HE) is a power-to-gas (P2G) electrochemical device that converts electrical energy into chemical energy by splitting water into hydrogen and oxygen. Among the various electrolysis technologies currently under development, the two main commercially available options are polymer electrolyte membrane water electrolyzers (PEMWE) and alkaline water electrolyzers (AWE). The primary distinction between these technologies lies in the ionic charge carrier and the nature of the electrolyte [1].

In power-to-gas applications, PEMWEs lead the market due to their high current densities and rapid dynamic response. These features allow for efficient energy conversion across short intervals, making them ideal for variable power loads typical of renewable sources [2, 3]. As a result, most green hydrogen projects with fluctuating power utilize PEMWE technology. Industrial examples include Siemens Energy's 200 MW plant for the Normand'Hy project [4] and the 20 MW facility from Iberdrola [5].

A promising application of HEs is their integration with renewable systems, specially wind farms. As the European power system transitions toward a low-inertia grid [6], wind farms are increasingly required to provide inertial support. This is commonly implemented by enabling a frequency-sensitive mode (FSM) in the active power control loop, typically via a power-frequency droop function, so that the active power output is adjusted as a function of the grid frequency. This strategy often requires power curtailment, thereby reducing the net energy yield. However, integrating HEs within wind farms can mitigate these losses while still providing the required inertial support. In those cases, the HE acts as a power-to-gas storage system that absorbs surplus wind power when the grid does not require it and, as a flexible load, it can provide inertial-like support by modulating its power consumption in response to frequency deviations [7]. This allows the wind farm to operate closer to its maximum power point while the HE performs the FSM function, provided that the electrolyzer capacity and operating range are adequately sized.

The demand-side flexibility of HEs is closely related to the characteristics of the hydrogen production process. First, several studies have shown that HE plants can adjust their power consumption very rapidly; experimental results on medium-scale electrolyzers indicate that the power set-point

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can be changed within a sub-second time frame [8]. Second, the produced hydrogen is typically stored in a large tank that acts as a buffer between hydrogen production and downstream hydrogen consumption. As a result, the hydrogen production rate, and thus the electrical power demand, can differ from the hydrogen consumption rate, provided that the tank inventory is sufficient to guarantee continuous supply to end users. Consequently, HEs can operate at different power set-points without directly affecting the downstream hydrogen consumption [9, 10].

Building on these demand-side flexibility characteristics, specifically the capability to operate at different power set-points and to rapidly adjust power consumption, HEs are regarded as promising candidates for frequency support in low-inertia power grids. The effectiveness of providing such support has been investigated in [7, 8, 11, 12, 13], where the HE plant is interfaced with the power grid through a voltage-source converter (VSC) operating in grid-following (GFL) mode with integrated FSM functionality. Moreover, the potential of HEs to operate in grid-forming mode has been explored in [14, 15].

Although using HEs for frequency support is attractive, the impact of such operation on the hydrogen production process and associated equipment still requires further investigation. Addressing this issue calls for a HE model that can capture the interactions between electrical demand and the internal physicochemical states of the plant. Dynamic modeling and control of water electrolysis systems is already a highly mature research area, with extensive literature already addressing phenomena such as internal electrochemical states, temperature evolution, or electrical transient behavior. Traditionally, various modeling approaches have been employed to represent these systems, with varying levels of detail depending on the research objective. The principal strategies are generally classified into: high-fidelity multiphysics models, lumped-parameter models and empirical models [16].

Multiphysics models are grounded in physical and electrochemical principles, using Partial Differential Equations (PDEs) to simulate the multidimensional (x, y, z) internal states of the electrolyzer. As demonstrated by [17, 18, 19], they are highly effective for design purposes, providing detailed insights into variables such as flow, temperature, and current distribution within the cell for a deeper spatial analysis. However, solving these PDEs across a spatial grid imposes a significant computational burden, making such models generally too slow for plant-level simulations [16].

Lumped models also rely on fundamental physics, but instead of using PDEs, they utilize Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs) and assume uniform system behavior, significantly reducing the computational burden associated with multiphysics approaches. While these models provide detailed access to key variables such as temperature, pressure, gas generation, and efficiency, related studies frequently focus solely on the electrolyzer and exclude the impact of peripheral equipment [20, 21, 22, 23]. For instance, the detailed models presented in [24, 25, 26] neglect Balance

of Plant (BoP) dynamics and are validated using controlled laboratory profiles rather than realistic operating scenarios. Furthermore, even studies that incorporate grid connections [27] or plant optimization [28] tend to omit the physical delays caused by water pumps, cooling systems, and compressors. As a result, the dynamic response of these models often appears unrealistically fast.

In contrast, empirical or equivalent circuit models [8, 29, 30] are generally derived from DC voltage or current measurements at the point of connection, inherently omitting internal states. As highlighted by [31, 32], these models successfully capture the aggregate dynamics of both the stack and its auxiliaries, and their mathematical simplicity makes them computationally fast. These characteristics make them highly suitable for power system studies and real-time electrolyzer control. However, this simplicity comes at the cost of losing explicit information about the internal states of the electrolyzer, preventing any detailed analysis of how operation impacts these underlying parameters [31].

Therefore, a clear need remains for a modeling approach that balances internal stack accuracy with the dynamic performance of peripheral equipment under realistic, megawatt-scale grid scenarios. To address this gap, this paper introduces a hybrid modeling framework for grid-connected HE plants that integrates physics-based lumped models with empirical models. By combining these strategies in a single framework, the hybrid model provides a comprehensive representation of the plant, capturing critical internal electrolyzer variables and simultaneously accounting for the aggregate response of peripheral equipment.

While most existing literature focuses on pilot-scale systems, this work explicitly targets the high-power profiles critical for industrial deployment. The case study comprises a 1000 MW wind farm connected to a weak AC grid, supplying a 100 MW constant load and a 500 MW electrolysis plant. This environment permits a detailed analysis of PEMWE plant behavior during frequency support operation within weak AC grids by capturing internal stack dynamics, thermal management, and storage fluctuations, while representing aggregate BoP delays through a first-order transfer function. Additionally, the proposed framework enables a dual-level analysis. First, it assesses how the provision of grid services affects the electrolyzer's internal integrity. Second, by acting as a virtual plant replica, it provides a robust foundation for digital twin (DT) applications, thereby enhancing operation, enabling informed decisions, and performance forecasting.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 establishes the fundamental modeling equations, and Section 3 details the steps followed for calibrating the model to the Siemens Silyzer 300. Then, the proposed case study is analyzed in Section 4, followed by a comprehensive evaluation of the plant's frequency support sensitivity under varying response times in Section 5. Finally, Section 7 summarizes the primary findings of the research.

Figure 1: Schematic of the HE plant: (a) electrical diagram of the electrolysis plant connected to an AC grid and a wind farm; (b) balance-of-plant components and hydrogen production process; (c) Silyzer 300 stack configuration; (d) operating principle of the PEM electrolysis cells.

2. Proposed hybrid dynamical model

This section details the hybrid dynamical framework developed to characterize the behavior of grid-connected HE plants. The model captures the interplay between internal electrochemical states and the aggregate response of the BoP equipment by integrating different model typologies, depending on the required level of detail. Further details on the modelling strategy are provided in the subsequent section.

2.1. Hybrid model architecture

The fundamental unit of a proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolysis system is the cell. As depicted in Fig. 1(d), each cell basically consists of two electrodes, an anode and a cathode, separated by a PEM. To achieve higher production capacities, these cells are generally assembled in series into an integrated unit known as stack. Commercially available stacks are typically rated for a maximum power between 0.5 and 1 MW [33] however, at industrial-scale demands, these power ranges are often insufficient. For such applications, multiple stacks can be interconnected for constructing a module, and a representative example of this architecture is the Siemens Energy Silyzer 300 (Fig. 1(c)), the reference system for this research. Consisting of 24 interconnected stacks, the module reaches a maximum power rating of 17.5 MW and manages operations like temperature regulation and gas storage collectively at the module level [34].

The case study presented in this article evaluates a 500 MW electrolysis system operating in tandem with an AC

grid, a constant load and a large-scale wind farm, what dictates the electrical power supplied to the hydrogen generation system. To achieve this capacity, n Silyzer 300 modules are aggregated to form the complete hydrogen plant architecture, as illustrated in Fig. 1(a).

The overall dynamics of HE plants are principally governed by: (i) the electrochemical and physical processes occurring within the electrolyzer stacks, (ii) module-level phenomena, such as temperature control and gas storage, and (iii) plant-level dynamics introduced by peripheral equipment, including pumps, separators, and compressors, as detailed in Fig. 1(b) [35, 36].

Building upon this context, and to align with the physical design of commercial electrolyzers, the proposed framework adopts a modular modeling approach with different levels of fidelity, to prevent overparameterization and optimize computational cost. Consequently, the proposed hybrid architecture can be sub-divided in three principal blocks:

- Stack: Utilizing a physics-based lumped strategy, this model captures the fundamental phenomena occurring at the anode, cathode, and membrane, alongside the terminal voltage. This detailed approach provides critical internal insights from the stack, such as gas generation rates.
- Module: The cooling loop and storage tanks, are modeled at module level. Employing a lumped approach for both cases, these two models represent the thermal inertia of the system and the pressure evolution of both storage tanks.

Figure 2: HE plant dynamical model

– Plant: Properly capturing the dynamics of BoP components is essential for having a representative HE plant model. By employing an empirical first-order transfer function, this can be achieved without sacrificing computational speed, representing the aggregated effect rather than modeling each component in detail.

Figure 2 illustrates the scaling of the hybrid model architecture, representing the plant as an ensemble of n modules containing m stacks each. Additionally, it outlines the governing equations for the principal system components, which will be detailed in the subsequent sections. The first-order transfer function is directly applied to the HE plant's input power profile, capturing the overall system dynamics.

With this context established, the remainder of this section is structured as follows: First, the stack model is presented, detailing the fundamental electrochemical equations. Next, module-level dynamics are introduced, encompassing models for thermal behavior and gas storage. Finally, plant-level dynamics are discussed, completing the formulation of the hybrid dynamical model.

2.2. HE stack model

The PEMWE stack model is founded on the fundamental electrochemical reactions that govern the water electrolysis process. While multiphysics models are ideal for understanding internal dynamics such as current and flow distributions, their heavy computational burden makes them unsuitable for power system studies involving multiple interconnected electrolysis stacks. Therefore, this work adopts a lumped-parameter formulation that assumes uniform spatial behavior, successfully capturing the essential internal states without sacrificing simulation speed. At this stage, the model focuses exclusively on the electrochemical behavior of the stack, independent of module and plant dynamics.

The model formulation adopts electrical current as the input and is structured into four distinct subsystems that represent the key components of the stack cells and their

core physicochemical phenomena: the anode, the cathode, the membrane, and the voltage characteristics [37, 38]. This modular approach allows for a precise characterization of the stack.

2.2.1. Anode

The anode is the location at which water oxidation occurs. As shown in Fig. 1(b), water is first collected in a storage tank and then delivered to the anode side of the PEM stack by a water pump. The DC voltage applied at the stack terminals drives the electrochemical reaction, causing the water molecules (H_2O) to split into hydrogen and oxygen (H_2 and O_2), as

The produced oxygen flows through a gas-water separator, where the residual water is removed and subsequently returned to the stack by a circulation pump. In the anode reaction, the generated protons (H^+) migrate through the membrane, while the electrons (e^-) flow through the external circuit, as observed at Fig. 1(d). The overall anode reaction can be expressed as

Based on the above, two mass balance equations are formulated:

– **Anode water balance:** is equal to the water that flows in, subtracted by the water flow that exits the system, the water consumption, and the amount dragged to the cathode as a consequence of diffusion and electro-osmotic phenomena, which happen on the membrane. It can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dN_{H_2O_{con}}}{dt} = & \dot{N}_{H_2O_{ai}} - \dot{N}_{H_2O_{ao}} - \dot{N}_{H_2O_{con}} \\ & - \dot{N}_{H_2O_{diff}} - \dot{N}_{H_2O_{eod}} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The flow that goes in is considered constant, while electro-osmotic and diffusion are calculated at the membrane block. The water consumption can be calculated with Faraday's equation and is related to the DC current applied (I), the number of cells (n), the Faradic efficiency (η_F), and the constant (F):

$$\dot{N}_{H_2O_{con}} = \frac{I \cdot n}{2 \cdot F} \cdot \eta_F \quad (4)$$

Faradic efficiency quantifies the fraction of applied electrical current, directly utilized for the electrochemical water-splitting reaction. For PEM electrolyzers, η_F ranges between 98% and 99% [37]. It is calculated using (5), where i denotes the current density (I divided by active area), and the parasitic loss i_{loss} which is approximated as 1%.

$$\eta_F = \frac{i - i_{loss}}{i} \quad (5)$$

– **Anode Oxygen Balance:** is equal to the mol that goes inside, the O_2 generated and the quantity that exits the anode:

$$\frac{dNO_2}{dt} = \dot{N}O_{2ai} + \dot{N}O_{2gen} - \dot{N}O_{2ao} \quad (6)$$

As no oxygen goes in, we could rewrite the equation as,

$$\frac{dNO_2}{dt} = \dot{N}O_{2gen} - \dot{N}O_{2ao} \quad (7)$$

The molar generation rate of oxygen ($\dot{N}O_{2,gen}$) is then obtained from Faraday's law, taking into account the stoichiometric coefficient of 1/2 in the overall reaction, as

$$\dot{N}O_{2,gen} = \frac{I \cdot n}{4F} \eta_F. \quad (8)$$

The outlet flow rates must also be determined. As a first step, the partial pressures of oxygen and water vapor in the anode gas compartment are computed using the ideal-gas law:

$$P_{O_2} = \frac{\dot{N}O_2 R_u T}{V_{an}} \quad (9)$$

$$P_{H_2O,an} = \frac{\dot{N}H_{2O,an} R_u T}{V_{an}} \quad (10)$$

where P_{O_2} and $P_{H_2O,an}$ are the partial pressures of oxygen and anode-side water vapor, respectively. $\dot{N}O_2$ and $\dot{N}H_{2O,an}$ are the corresponding numbers of moles, R_u is the universal gas constant V_{an} is the anode gas control volume.

Assuming that oxygen and water vapor are the dominant species in the anode compartment, and that the total pressure P_{an} is known, Dalton's law can be applied to determine their respective molar fractions:

$$P_{an} = P_{O_2} + P_{H_2O,an} \quad (11)$$

$$y_{O_2} = \frac{P_{O_2}}{P_{an}} \quad (12)$$

$$y_{H_2O,an} = \frac{P_{H_2O,an}}{P_{an}} \quad (13)$$

The total anode outlet flow can be calculated using the working electrolyzer pressure (P_{el}) and the anode outlet flow coefficient (k_{ao}), which is equal to 0.95 mol/(Pa · s) [37], as follows:

$$\dot{N}_{ao} = k_{ao}(P_{an} - P_{el}) \quad (14)$$

Combining this value with the molar fractions obtained, the oxygen and water outlet flows are calculated,

$$\dot{N}O_{2ao} = \dot{N}_{ao} \cdot y_{O_2} \quad (15)$$

$$\dot{N}H_{2O_{2ao}} = \dot{N}_{ao} \cdot y_{H_2O_{an}} \quad (16)$$

2.2.2. Cathode

At the cathode, the reduction half-reaction takes place. The hydrogen ions generated at the anode migrate through the membrane and recombine with electrons to form gaseous hydrogen, as

The produced hydrogen is passed through a gas separator to eliminate the remaining water in the gas. After cooling down in a heat exchanger, hydrogen is passed through the gas condensate and de-oxygenation. Then, it is fed into a gas dryer through a compressor. Finally, the produced hydrogen is stored in the tank, which acts as a buffer between hydrogen production and consumption. The hydrogen production in the cathode has two molar flow balances, which are described below.

– **Cathode water balance:** The mass balance could be considered as follows:

$$\frac{dNH_2O_{ca}}{dt} = \dot{N}H_2O_{ci} - \dot{N}H_2O_{co} + \dot{N}H_2O_{eod} + \dot{N}H_2O_{diff} \quad (18)$$

In this case, there isn't a direct injection of H_2O , so $\dot{N}H_2O_{ci}$ is zero, and the water flow that goes in is a consequence of the phenomena that happen in the membrane:

$$\frac{dNH_2O_{ca}}{dt} = -\dot{N}H_2O_{co} + \dot{N}H_2O_{eod} + \dot{N}H_2O_{diff} \quad (19)$$

– **Cathode hydrogen balance:** The flow is equal to the amount generated subtracted by the existing quantity:

$$\frac{dNH_2}{dt} = \dot{N}H_{2ci} + \dot{N}H_{2gen} - \dot{N}H_{2co} \quad (20)$$

As there is no inlet of hydrogen, the equation depends only on two terms,

$$\frac{dNH_2}{dt} = \dot{N}H_{2gen} - \dot{N}H_{2co} \quad (21)$$

To calculate the produced hydrogen, Faraday's equation is used,

$$\dot{N}H_{2gen} = \frac{n \cdot I}{2 \cdot F} \cdot \eta_F \quad (22)$$

Also, the Ideal Gas equation is applied for calculating the pressures of each component:

$$PH_2 = \frac{\dot{N}H_2 \cdot R_u \cdot T}{V_{ca}} \quad (23)$$

$$PH_2O_{ca} = \frac{\dot{N}H_2O_{ca} \cdot R_u \cdot T}{V_{ca}} \quad (24)$$

$$P_{ca} = PH_2 + PH_2O_{ca} \quad (25)$$

Then the molar fractions are obtained as,

$$y_{H_2} = \frac{PH_2}{P_{ca}} \quad (26)$$

$$y_{H_2O_{ca}} = \frac{PH_2O_{ca}}{P_{ca}} \quad (27)$$

The molar flow that goes out of the cathode (\dot{N}_{co}) is obtained based on the flow coefficient ($k_{co}=0.45$) mol/(Pa·s) [37], the pressure at cathode (P_{ca}) and the desired working pressure (P_{el}). There is no flow out of the cathode till the pressure inside is greater than the desired working value,

$$\dot{N}_{co} = \begin{cases} k_{co}(P_{co} - P_{el}) & \text{if } P_{co} \geq P_{el} \\ 0 & \text{if } P_{co} < P_{el} \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

Finally, hydrogen and water outlet flows are obtained as

$$\dot{N}_{H_2co} = \dot{N}_{co} \cdot y_{H_2} \quad (29)$$

$$\dot{N}_{H_2O_{2co}} = \dot{N}_{co} \cdot y_{H_2O_{ca}}. \quad (30)$$

2.2.3. Membrane

The membrane is responsible for enabling H^+ transfer between the electrodes, electrically insulating them, and preventing product crossover. As mentioned in previous sections and illustrated in Fig. 1(d), there is also a water flux through the membrane, which can be decomposed into two phenomena: diffusion and electro-osmotic drag. Both contributions depend on the water content within the membrane.

– **Electro-osmotic drag:** In PEM electrolyzers, 3-4 molecules of H_2O are typically transported through the membrane per proton conducted [38]. The corresponding water molar flow rate, $\dot{N}_{H_2O,eod}$, is given by

$$\dot{N}_{H_2O,eod} = \frac{n_d i A}{F}, \quad (31)$$

where F is the Faraday constant, A is the active cell area, and i is the current density. The electro-osmotic drag coefficient n_d is computed as

$$n_d = 0.0029 \lambda_m^2 + 0.05 \lambda_m - 3.4 \times 10^{-19}, \quad (32)$$

where λ_m denotes the mean membrane water content, a critical parameter governing the membrane ability to transport H^+ . Physically, λ_m represents the degree of hydration within the PEM membrane, driven by the water activities at the anode and cathode (a_{an} and a_{ca}) which indicate the available water at both sides of the cell. These activities are evaluated using the saturation pressure (P_{sat}) at operating conditions alongside the previously derived partial pressures of water, $P_{H_2O,an}$ and $P_{H_2O,ca}$.

$$a_{an} = \frac{P_{H_2O,an}}{P_{sat}} \quad (33)$$

$$a_{ca} = \frac{P_{H_2O,ca}}{P_{sat}} \quad (34)$$

$$P_{sat}(T) = -2846.4 + 411.24 T - 10.554 T^2 + 0.16636 T^3 \quad (35)$$

It is considered that the behavior of the gas mixture is ideal, that's why the expression for water activities is the same as the relative humidity. Once a_{an} and a_{ca} are known, λ_{an} and λ_{ca} can be calculated,

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_i &= 0.43 + 17.18 \cdot a_i - 39.85 \cdot a_i^2 \\ &\quad + 36 \cdot a_i^3 \quad 0 < a_i \leq 1 \\ \lambda_i &= 14 + 1.4 \cdot (a_i - 1) \quad 1 < a_i \leq 3 \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

Then the membrane water content (λ_m) is equal to:

$$\lambda_m = \frac{\lambda_{an} + \lambda_{ca}}{2} \quad (37)$$

– **Diffusion:** the particles of water are injected at the anode and tend to travel to a place where the concentration is lower (cathode). Such phenomena are represented by applying the first law of Fick:

$$\dot{N}_{H_2O_{diff}} = D_w \cdot \frac{C_{wc} - C_{wa}}{t_{me}} \quad (38)$$

where t_{me} represents the membrane thickness and D_w is the water diffusion coefficient. The driving force for this diffusion is the concentration gradient between the cathode C_{wc} and anode C_{wa} boundaries. These concentrations, within both sides of the cell, are calculated using the membrane's dry density ρ_{me} [39], its equivalent weight EW_{me} [40], and the specific water content λ_i :

$$C_{wa} = \frac{\rho_{me}}{EW_{me}} \lambda_{an} \quad (39)$$

$$C_{wc} = \frac{\rho_{me}}{EW_{me}} \lambda_{ca} \quad (40)$$

The diffusion coefficient D_w can be calculated as:

$$D_w = D_\lambda \cdot \exp \left[2416 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{300} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \right], \quad (41)$$

where the exponential term employs an Arrhenius formulation to account for temperature dependence. Furthermore, because diffusivity varies significantly with membrane hydration, D_λ defines the diffusion coefficient as a direct function of the mean membrane water content:

$$\begin{aligned} D_\lambda &= 10^{-10} & \lambda_m \leq 2 \\ D_\lambda &= 10^{-10} \cdot (1 + 2 \cdot (\lambda_m - 2)) & 2 < \lambda_m \leq 3 \\ D_\lambda &= 10^{-10} \cdot (3 - 1.76 \cdot (\lambda_m - 3)) & 3 < \lambda_m \leq 4.5 \\ D_\lambda &= 1.25 \cdot 10^{-10} & 4.5 < \lambda_m \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

2.2.4. Voltage

The stack DC is treated as an input parameter, and the resulting cell voltage is computed from the open-circuit

voltage V_{ocv} and the activation, ohmic, and mass-transfer overpotentials, V_{act} , V_{ohm} , and V_{mt} , respectively:

$$V_{cell} = V_{ocv} + V_{act} + V_{ohm} + V_{mt}. \quad (43)$$

The mass-transfer overpotential V_{mt} becomes significant only at high current densities (typically above 3 A/cm²), which lie outside the operating range considered in this study. Therefore, V_{mt} is neglected and the cell voltage is approximated as

$$V_{cell} = V_{ocv} + V_{act} + V_{ohm}. \quad (44)$$

First, the open-circuit voltage (V_{ocv}) is defined as the cell potential under zero-current conditions. It is calculated using the Nernst equation:

$$V_{ocv} = V_{rev} + \frac{RT}{2F} \ln(q), \quad (45)$$

where V_{rev} is the reversible cell voltage, R is the universal gas constant, T is the stack temperature, and F is the Faraday constant. The water activity between anode and electrolyte, a_{H_2O} , is assumed to be unity in this work [38]. The reaction quotient q can be defined in several ways, as discussed in [24]. In many models, q is set to 1 because the partial pressures of the gaseous species inside the electrolyzer are not explicitly evaluated. This approximation, however, neglects the effect of operating pressure on the open-circuit voltage. In the proposed model, q is expressed in terms of the partial pressures of hydrogen, oxygen, and water in the electrolyzer, denoted by P_{H_2} , P_{O_2} , and P_{H_2O} , respectively, as

$$q = \frac{P_{H_2} \sqrt{P_{O_2}}}{P_{H_2O}}. \quad (46)$$

The reversible voltage V_{rev} is dependent on the Gibbs free energy of water formation (ΔG), 236.48 kJ/mol. In addition, V_{rev} is related to the operational temperature, as proposed at [41]:

$$V_{rev} = \Delta G(2F)^{-1} - 8.5 \cdot 10^{-4}(T - 298) \quad (47)$$

Next, the activation overpotential V_{act} is given by the sum of the anode and cathode contributions:

$$V_{act} = V_{act,an} + V_{act,ca} \quad (48)$$

$$V_{act,an} = \frac{RT}{2\alpha_{an}F} \ln\left(\frac{i}{i_{0,an}}\right) \quad (49)$$

$$V_{act,ca} = \frac{RT}{2\alpha_{ca}F} \ln\left(\frac{i}{i_{0,ca}}\right) \quad (50)$$

Charge transfer coefficients (α_{an} and α_{ca}) and exchange current densities ($i_{0,an}$ and $i_{0,ca}$) are parameters used for fitting the polarization curve of the model with experimental data, so they change depending on the type of electrolyzer. In this case, they have been taken from [24] where a model for a Silyzer 300 is calibrated with experimental data: α_{an} and

α_{ca} are considered to be 0.5, $i_{0,an}$ is equal to $1.0000001 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and $i_{0,ca}$ is 0.278 [24].

Then, the ohmic overpotential (V_{ohm}) can be calculated with the help of Ohm's Law.

$$V_{ohm} = i \cdot R_{ohm} \quad (51)$$

The resistance R_{ohm} can be calculated with the thickness t_{me} and the conductivity σ_m of the membrane :

$$R_{ohm} = \frac{t_{me}}{\sigma_m} \quad (52)$$

The conductivity represents the capability of the PEM membrane to transport H^+ protons, from anode to cathode. Given its strong dependence on operating temperature and membrane hydration, it is defined as:

$$\sigma_m = (0.00514\lambda_m - 0.00326) \cdot \exp\left[1268 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{303} - \frac{1}{T}\right)\right] \quad (53)$$

Once V_{cell} is known, the efficiency η_{el} can be calculated knowing the minimum voltage (V_{th}) required to start the electrolytic reaction.

$$V_{th} = \frac{\Delta H}{2F} = 1.481 \text{ V} \quad (54)$$

$$\eta_{el} = \frac{V_{th}}{V_{cell}} \quad (55)$$

Considering that all the cells behave electrically in the same way (having the same current and voltage), it can be considered that the voltage of the electrolyzer V_{stack} is equal to V_{cell} multiplied by the number of cells (n_{cells}).

$$V_{stack} = V_{cell} \cdot n_{cells} \quad (56)$$

Assuming this, the minimum voltage follows the same relation, so the stack efficiency is the same as η_{el} .

2.3. HE Module Model

Most available studies utilizing physics-based stack models are typically developed for low-power electrolyzers (on the order of 1.5–5 kW), focusing strictly on internal stack dynamics while often neglecting factors like thermal behavior or storage tank pressures [42]. Capturing these system-level dynamics is essential for accurately representing real-world, large-scale electrolysis plants.

Standard commercial electrolyzer stacks typically operate within the 0.5–1 MW range, and to achieve higher power ratings, these units are generally arrayed in series or parallel. For instance, the Silyzer 300 comprises 24 individual 0.7 MW stacks, yielding a total module capacity of 17.5 MW. In such commercial setups, thermal management and gas storage are centralized at the module level [33].

Consequently, in addition to modeling the stacks, this work incorporates two further models to accurately capture the evolution of both temperature and storage pressure at the module level. The fundamentals of these additional models are detailed in the following section and provide a more realistic representation of real-world plant operation.

Figure 3: PEM electrolyzer CV heat balance

2.3.1. Thermal

Commercial PEM electrolyzers typically operate in the temperature range of 25 to 90°C, with the exact limits depending on the manufacturer. At higher temperatures, the membrane electrode assembly (MEA) loses stability, reducing both efficiency and durability. At lower temperatures, the ohmic resistance is higher making the system less efficient, which translates into higher energy losses. This highlights the need to control the stack temperature to prevent potential damage and ensure optimal operation [43].

From a modeling perspective, the thermal behavior of an electrolyzer can be represented with varying levels of complexity. Multiphysics models, such as three dimensional models, can capture the heat distribution across all spatial dimensions (x, y, and z), enabling a detailed understanding of flow and temperature gradients [18]. Alternatively, two dimensional models simplify the problem by considering only the x and y axes [44], representing the cross sectional area of the cells. Although these distributed models are optimal for stack design, hot spot detection, and degradation forecasting, they are highly complex and computationally heavy [45], making them unsuitable for plant monitoring and dynamic control.

Alternatively, lumped models are among the most widely used approaches for thermal modeling [46, 47]. Since the initial model proposed by [48], several variations have been developed, making this approach the standard choice for plant oriented studies. These models generally assume a uniform system temperature. While this simplification reduces precision, the computational demand is significantly lower than other options. Moreover, lumped models have proven sufficient accuracy to capture overall electrolyzer performance [49, 24, 50].

This study employs an advanced lumped model for two primary reasons. First, the objective is to estimate the energy required for module temperature regulation, rather than analyzing localized internal cell phenomena. Second, because the thermal model must run concurrently with additional more complex models, and a lumped approach allows to

keep the computational burden manageable during dynamic simulations. Furthermore, while applied at the module level here to optimize simulation speed, this approach is fully adaptable and could be extended to every individual stack comprising the electrolysis system.

The considered thermal model expands upon the approach from [48] by incorporating the dynamic influence of the inlet and outlet flows. Assuming that all cells and stacks behave identically, and treating the entire electrolyzer as a single control volume (CV) as illustrated in Fig. 3, the overall heat balance based on the First Law of Thermodynamics is expressed as:

$$\frac{dE}{dt} = \dot{Q}_{gen} + \sum (\dot{m}_i h_i)_{in} - \sum (\dot{m}_i h_i)_{out} - \dot{Q}_{loss} + \dot{Q}_{need}, \quad (57)$$

where

– $\frac{dE}{dt}$ represents the rate of change of internal energy inside the stack and can be expressed as

$$\frac{dE}{dt} = \frac{d(C_{p,i} V_i \rho_i T)}{dt}, \quad (58)$$

where V_i is the control volume of the electrolyzer, $C_{p,i}$ is the specific heat capacity at constant pressure, ρ_i is the density, and T is the temperature. Since the control volume is predominantly filled with water, the density and heat capacity are assumed constant and equal to those of liquid water, i.e., $C_{p,i} = C_{p,H_2O}$ and $\rho_i = \rho_{H_2O}$. Under this assumption, the expression simplifies to

$$\frac{dE}{dt} = C_{p,H_2O} V_i \rho_{H_2O} \frac{dT}{dt}. \quad (59)$$

– \dot{Q}_{gen} : Since not all the electrical energy supplied to the stack is converted into chemical energy stored in hydrogen, the remaining portion is released as heat and is denoted by \dot{Q}_{gen} . It can be written as

$$\dot{Q}_{gen} = W (1 - \eta_{el}), \quad (60)$$

where W is the electrical power input to the stack and η_{el} is the electrolyzer efficiency. Assuming that all cells behave identically and denoting by n the number of cells in the stack, the electrical power input is given by

$$W = I V_{cell} n, \quad (61)$$

being I the stack current and V_{cell} the voltage per cell.

– $\sum (\dot{m}_i \cdot h_i)_{in}$: Represents the energy provided by the flows that go inside the CV, that in this case is just H_2O that comes recirculated at the anode, at working temperature

$$\sum (\dot{m}_i \cdot h_i)_{in} = \dot{m}_{H_2O_{ai}} \cdot h_{H_2O_{ai}}. \quad (62)$$

- $\sum (\dot{m}_i \cdot h_i)_{out}$: Corresponds to the energy of the flows that go outside the CV, which in this case are: H_2 , O_2 , and mainly H_2O .

$$\sum (\dot{m}_i \cdot h_i)_{out} = \dot{m}_{H_2O_{co}} \cdot h_{H_2O_{co}} + \dot{m}_{H_2co} \cdot h_{H_2co} + \dot{m}_{O_2ao} \cdot h_{O_2ao} \quad (63)$$

- \dot{Q}_{need} : Stands for the heat needed to control the system at the desired temperature. To make it as realistic as possible, it has been considered a water heat exchanger that depends on the desired (T_{ref}) and electrolyzer temperature (T).

$$\dot{Q}_{need} = \dot{m}_{H_2O_{ht}} \cdot C_p_{H_2O} \cdot (T_{ref} - T) \quad (64)$$

- \dot{Q}_{loss} : It is also important to take into account the heat dissipated to the environment due to convection and radiation phenomena, supposing that the electrolyzer isn't isolated.

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{Q}_{loss} &= \dot{Q}_{conv} + \dot{Q}_{rad} \\ &= (h_c + h_r) \cdot A_{ext} \cdot (T - T_{env}) \end{aligned} \quad (65)$$

Where A_{ext} is the external area of the electrolyzer, T is the temperature of the electrolyzer, T_{env} is the environment temperature (25°C), h_c and h_r correspond to the conductive and radiative heat transfer coefficients that are calculated depending on the characteristics of the system.

- h_c : It can be calculated knowing the Nusselt Number, the thermal conductivity (for air $k_m=0.026 \text{ Wm}\cdot\text{K}$) and the electrolyzer length (L).

$$h_c = \frac{\mathcal{N}_u \cdot k_m}{L} \quad (66)$$

Considering the electrolyzer as a rectangular body subjected to slow forced convection in air with a free-stream velocity of approximately 0.2 m/s, and assuming a Reynolds number $Re = 5000$ and a Prandtl number $Pr = 0.7$, the Nusselt number can be estimated as

$$\mathcal{N}_u = 0.66 \cdot Re^{0.675} \cdot Pr^{1/3}. \quad (67)$$

- h_r : This parameter is estimated from the surface emissivity of the material ($\epsilon = 0.6$ for rough stainless steel), the Stefan-Boltzmann constant ($\sigma = 5.67 \times 10^{-8} \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2 \text{ K}^4)$), and the mean temperature between the stack surface and the ambient, T_m . It is given by

$$h_r = 4 \cdot \epsilon \cdot \sigma \cdot T_m^3 \quad (68)$$

2.3.2. Storage

In any commercial hydrogen electrolysis plant, the produced gases are first transferred to buffer storage tanks, as illustrated in Fig. 1(b), from which they supply the downstream demand. While some facilities connect these tanks directly to consumers via pipelines, others rely on periodic discharges by transport tankers [51, 4]. The case study presented in this article couples an electrolysis plant with a wind

farm. Because such renewable generation sites are typically geographically isolated, it is assumed that the hydrogen and oxygen tanks are fully discharged into transport trucks or ships every two to three days.

For these stationary applications, metallic pressure vessels operating between 150 and 300 bar [52] remain the industry standard due to their proven reliability, and are therefore adopted in this work. To manage the inherent mismatch between production and consumption, the storage facility must be carefully sized according to the HE capabilities. The specific methodology for determining the required tank volumes is detailed in Section 3.4.2, following the definition of the system's operational boundaries [53].

In addition to sizing the tank volumes, continuous monitoring of the tank pressure is crucial for safety and understanding the effects of plant operation. To capture the dynamic pressure evolution within the storage tanks, the rate of change is defined by the mass balance and the Ideal Gas Law:

$$\frac{dP_{tx}}{dt} = z \cdot \frac{R_u \cdot T_{tx}}{V_{tx}} \left(\sum \dot{N}_{tx,in} - \sum \dot{N}_{tx,out} \right) \quad (69)$$

where P_{tx} denotes the pressure within the tank, the subscript t designates tank-related variables, and x specifies the type of gas stored ($x \in \{H_2, O_2\}$). The term z represents the compressibility factor, which is assumed to be 1 under ideal gas conditions. $\dot{N}_{tx,in}$ and $\dot{N}_{tx,out}$ are the inlet and outlet molar flow rates of the tanks, respectively. T_{tx} and V_{tx} correspond to the operating temperature and volume of the tank. Consequently, the instantaneous tank pressure is determined by integrating the rate of change $\frac{dP_{tx}}{dt}$, added to the initial tank pressure (P_{tx0}). This straightforward approach avoids unnecessarily increasing the computational burden and is consistent with established methodologies [54, 24].

Storage tank temperature is also a critical parameter, as it directly influences gas properties and internal pressure. In this study, T_{tx} is fixed at a constant 25°C for both gases across all simulations. While implementing a dynamic thermal balance to evaluate the effects of ambient conditions and inlet/outlet flows on tank temperature would be valuable, it falls outside the scope of the present work and remains an objective for future research. However, if the model is used in a DT application, tank temperatures measured from the physical system could be directly assigned to T_{tx} to achieve a better understanding of pressure dynamics.

Having outlined the principal characteristics of the thermal and storage models, the discussion now transitions to the overall plant model [55].

2.4. HE plant model

The stack model and the module level algorithms, provide a deep insight into the internal behavior of HE, yet they do not contain the dynamics of the plant's peripheral equipment, such as water pumps, fans, heat exchangers, etc. Such plant dynamics are essential for grid-connection studies where an accurate dynamical response from HE plant to

Figure 4: DC current response of a 40 kW HE plant to setpoint changes

the voltage and frequency events is critical for power system studies. While the exact modeling of all plant peripheral equipment is very complex, several studies concluded that such complex modeling might not be necessary [8, 29].

In fact, the DC current dynamic of the HE plant resembles a first-order dynamical response in the event of a change in active power setpoint. This is experimentally verified in [8] where the power reference of the HE is rapidly changed and the resulting DC current is plotted. As shown in Fig. 4, the power consumption is changed (a) from 25% to 100%, (b) from 50% to 100%, and (c) from 75% to 100%, and the DC current of HE is plotted for every case. The DC current response has a time-constant (τ_h) of about 30 ms. Hence, the overall dynamics of HE plant equipment can be approximated as a first-order function [29, 56]:

$$I_{dc}(t) = I_m (1 - \exp(-t/\tau_h)) \quad (70)$$

where I_m is the peak of DC current (1 p.u.). However, the evaluation presented in [8] is based on a 40 kW HE case study. To ensure a realistic dynamic response for a MW-scale system, the DC current response time constant (τ_h) must be scaled up. Because MW-scale plants achieve their target power by connecting arrays such as the Silyzer 300 in parallel [57], τ_h inherently requires adjustment for these high-power configurations. Given its significance, the impact of τ_h on the plant's frequency response will be analyzed in subsequent sections.

3. HE model calibration and optimal operation

Once the mathematical fundamentals have been outlined, the proposed HE hybrid model has been calibrated to replicate the behavior of the Silyzer 300, a 17.5 MW PEM electrolyzer manufactured by Siemens. The following sections outline the data available for adapting the hybrid model to this commercial unit, define its operational limits and optimal working conditions. Then, further details are given about the sizing of the storage and thermal systems.

Table 1

Silyzer 300 17.5 MW HE principal characteristics

Parameter	Units	Value	Source
Rated power	MW	17.5	[59]
Rated H ₂ production	kg/h	335	[59]
System efficiency	%	76	[59]
N ^o of stack	-	24	[58]
Water requirement	l/h	4,700	[34]
Minimum load	%	5	[59]
Dimensions (W/D/H)	m	15/7.5/7.3	[58]
N ^o of cells per module	-	25	[24]
Active area	cm ²	6,000	[24]
Thickness membrane	mm	0.178	[24]

3.1. Available Silyzer 300 information

According to Siemens, each electrolyzer module comprises 24 stacks connected in parallel, as can be observed in Fig.1(c), with each stack containing 25 cells. The main technical specifications of the Silyzer 300, as reported in the manufacturer's technical documentation and other publicly available information [34, 58, 59], are listed in Table 1.

Additional parameters not provided by the manufacturer, including the cell active area, membrane thickness, and the number of cells per module were extracted from [24], a study that defines the data required to accurately model this particular electrolyzer.

While these sources provided the majority of the required data, a specific set of assumptions have been necessary to align the model with the actual operation of the electrolyzer.

First, because official performance data are only available at the module level, it is assumed that all 24 stacks operate identically. Second, the operational metrics provided by Siemens [34, 58, 59], such as rated power, hydrogen production, and overall system efficiency, are assumed to correspond to operation at maximum continuous power. Finally, in accordance with established literature [24], these values are assumed to be reported at standard reference conditions of 1 bar and 60°C.

Building upon these parameters and assumptions, the following section presents the validation of the physics-based stack model and establishes the operational boundaries of the PEMWE stack, ensuring its accurate representation under dynamic operating conditions.

3.2. Stack model validation and operational boundaries

Based on the available information and the developed model, it is possible to estimate the operational range of a single stack. Assuming that the 24 stacks of the Silyzer 300 operate under identical conditions, and considering 335 kg/h as the maximum hydrogen production rate of the entire HE module, a single stack is expected to produce 13.96 kg/h.

The stack model was executed over a current density range of 0–3 A/cm², at 1 bar and 60 °C, corresponding to the

Figure 5: Simulation of a single Silyzer 300 stack at 1 bar and 60 °C for a current density sweep from 0 to 3 A/cm², used to estimate operating limits and validate the model. Top: cell voltage polarization curve. Bottom: hydrogen mass flow rate.

Table 2

Estimated operating limits of a single Silyzer 300 stack

Parameter	Units	Max.	Min.
Cell current density	A/cm ²	2.50	0.16
Stack current	A	15,000	960
Power	kW	728.21	36.41
Cell voltage	V	1.94	1.49
Stack Efficiency	%	76.32	99.71
H ₂ production	kg/h	13.96	0.93

operational conditions reported in [24], and the results are presented in Fig. 5. The simulation results and the polarization curve shown in the top plot are in close agreement with those reported by [24], confirming the representativeness of the model.

As shown in the bottom graph of Fig. 5, the hydrogen generation rate of a single stack reaches its maximum expected hydrogen generation of 13.96 kg/h at a current density of 2.50 A/cm². This current density therefore, represents the upper operating limit of the electrolyzer. From this observation and based on the model results, the operation of the stack at maximum power can be derived.

Siemens defines the minimum operating power of the Silyzer 300 as 5% of the maximum, which is translated into a current density of 0.16 A/cm². Following the same approach as before and by taking as a reference the simulation results, this value determines the lower operational limits of a single stack. The principal parameters related to the HE stack

Figure 6: Polarization characteristics of the Silyzer 300 at different operating temperatures, with a stack pressure of 1 bar and current within the nominal operating range. Left: cell voltage (blue). Right: cell efficiency (red).

operational at maximum and minimum power are presented in Table 2.

The results reflect the typical behavior of PEMWE, where the efficiency is higher at lower current levels, reaching 99.71% at 960 A, the minimum operating current. Conversely, at the maximum current of 15,000 A, the efficiency decreases to 76.32%. This value is 0.3% higher than the 76% reported by the manufacturer, most likely due to unmodeled power consumption and losses associated with the balance of plant, which reduce the overall module efficiency.

3.3. Optimal working conditions

Specific information about the operating temperature and pressure of the Silyzer 300 is not publicly available. However, commercial PEM electrolyzers typically operate between 20 and 90 °C [43] and at pressures ranging from 1 to 30 bar [60] [3].

In most studies, the electrolyzer performance is modeled at fixed temperature and pressure conditions, without fully accounting for how these factors influence overall efficiency [24] [30]. In this work, the proposed model includes the effects of both temperature and pressure on stack performance, allowing a detailed analysis from the stack perspective to identify the optimal operating point for maximum efficiency.

3.3.1. Temperature

The model was evaluated at four stack temperatures (25, 40, 60, and 80 °C) while maintaining a constant stack pressure of 1 bar, with the objective of identifying the optimal operating temperature. As illustrated in Fig. 6, the system exhibits the highest efficiency at 80 °C, reflecting improved electrochemical and transport properties. In contrast, operation at lower temperatures, such as 25 °C, results in higher cell voltages and reduced performance. It is also observed that, at low current densities, the influence of temperature on efficiency is relatively small; however, when the current density exceeds 0.5 A/cm², the impact of the thermal conditions becomes more pronounced.

This can be explained because at higher temperatures, less energy is required to dissociate water molecules, catalyst activity improves, and membrane conductivity increases,

Figure 7: Polarization characteristics of the Silyzer 300 at different operating pressures and a stack temperature of 25 °C and current within the nominal operating range. Left: cell voltage (blue). Right: cell efficiency (red).

collectively reducing ohmic losses and lowering cell voltage. Nevertheless, operation above 90 °C accelerates degradation processes in the PEM, potentially leading to vapor formation within the cell. At the same time, operation near ambient temperature can promote adverse effects such as platinum catalyst poisoning [61]. Considering these factors, 80 °C was identified as the optimal operating temperature for maximizing efficiency. This setpoint provides a critical 10 °C safety margin against the 90 °C threshold, preventing fast membrane degradation.

3.3.2. Pressure

The same procedure was followed in this case, applying pressures of 1, 10, 20, and 30 Bar (Figure 7), while maintaining the temperature constant at 25 °C. Lower pressures result in higher efficiencies, a behavior that can be explained by the fact that increasing the operating pressure raises the membrane resistance and consequently the ohmic losses, leading to higher cell voltages and reduced efficiency.

However, from a plant-level standpoint, operating at elevated pressures can be advantageous for hydrogen and oxygen separation, as it mitigates hydrogen crossover and yields gases of higher purity [62]. Additionally, since hydrogen is typically stored in tanks at pressures exceeding 200 bar, higher HE operating pressures can simplify downstream processes and improve overall efficiency. Nevertheless, elevated pressures are also associated with accelerated membrane degradation, which may negatively affect system durability [61].

In this particular study, since the electrolyzer is intended to operate as an intermittent load utilizing surplus renewable energy, operation at 1 bar is considered the most suitable option, offering improved durability, faster dynamic response, and higher overall efficiency.

3.4. HE module operation

Following the validation of the single stack model and the identification of optimal operating conditions (1 bar, 80°C), the system is scaled up to represent a complete Silyzer 300 module. This configuration comprises 24 individual stacks, which are assumed to operate uniformly.

Table 3
Silyzer 300 estimated module operation limits

Parameter	Units	Max.	Min.
Current	kA	360.00	23.04
Power	MW	17.49	0.87
Module Efficiency	%	76.32	99.71
H ₂ production	kg/h	335.00	22.32

Table 3 outlines the principal parameters defining the operational boundaries of this HE module. Within these limits, the applied electrical power dictates overall performance. While hydrogen and oxygen production are proportional to input power, higher power levels simultaneously increase energy losses, leading to a reduction in system efficiency.

Having established these operational boundaries, the subsequent sections detail the sizing of the thermal system and storage tanks required to safely support the module's continuous operation.

3.4.1. Thermal system

Heat generation within the electrolyzer module is inversely correlated with efficiency. Operation at lower power levels yields higher stack efficiencies and, consequently, reduced heat generation. Specifically, at the minimum operational power of 0.87 MW, where the system achieves an efficiency of 99.71%, internal heat generation is insufficient to maintain the optimal operating temperature of 80°C, necessitating supplemental heating. Conversely, at the maximum power of 17.49 MW, energy losses increase and heat generation becomes substantial. With 23.68% of the applied power dissipating as heat, active cooling becomes strictly necessary to maintain the desired thermal equilibrium and ensure the safety of the HE.

The system overall thermal balance is constrained by the flows entering and exiting the electrolyzer, internal heat generation, and heat losses, as defined in Eq. 57. Within this equation, \dot{Q}_{need} represents the energy demand required to maintain the desired operating temperature. Because the system considers a water-based heat exchanger with a constant specific heat capacity, the dynamic thermal response is strictly governed by adjusting the cooling water mass flow rate ($\dot{m}H_2O_{ht}$).

Under dynamic conditions, if this cooling capacity (\dot{Q}_{need}) is insufficient to dissipate the generated heat, thermal energy accumulates within the electrolyzer, inducing a temperature rise. To prevent irreversible degradation of the PEM, the model enforces a critical safety constraint: if the internal temperature exceeds the maximum allowable threshold of 90°C, the system automatically curtails input power to its minimum operational level until thermal equilibrium is restored. Having thus established the thermal management strategy, the focus now shifts to sizing the storage tanks.

Table 4
Storage tank specification for Silyzer 300 module

Parameter	Units	Value
Operational tank pressure	bar	5-300
H ₂ volume	m ³	1180
O ₂ volume	m ³	590
Storage capacity	h	72

3.4.2. Storage tank size

As previously introduced, stationary gas storage systems typically operate at a maximum pressure of 300 bar. To determine the required tank volumes, a three-day storage capacity is assumed, based on the Silyzer 300's maximum hydrogen production rate of 167.5 kmol/h. Although at the dynamic simulation the operating tank temperature is fixed at a constant 25°C (as defined in Section 2.3.2), the physical volumes were conservatively sized assuming a gas temperature of 80°C. This assumption introduces a built-in safety margin to the overall tank design.

Applying the ideal gas law under these conditions yields required volumes of approximately 1180 m³ for hydrogen and 590 m³ for oxygen, as summarized in Table 4. During operation, the tank pressure is strictly constrained between 5 and 300 bar. The 5 bar minimum threshold protects peripheral equipment, such as pumps and compressors, while simultaneously preventing external contamination [52], whereas the 300 bar maximum is dictated by the structural limitations of the storage technology. Similar to the thermal management strategy, the model incorporates a protective control margin to prevent the system from reaching these limits. Specifically, the electrolyzer stops production 1 bar before either boundary is reached. Furthermore, because the HE operates at a lower pressure, achieving these elevated storage values will necessitate additional compression between the electrolyzer outlet and the storage tanks, which entails a higher overall energy consumption.

Once the Silyzer 300 model has been calibrated and the module's operational boundaries have been defined, it is possible to proceed to the case study, where the specific plant configuration is outlined alongside its response characteristics.

4. Grid-connection case study

The proposed hybrid dynamical model of the electrolyzer is used in the AC network outlined in Fig. 8. The 500 MW HE and a 100 MW constant load are connected to a 220 kV bus, which is supplied by two parallel lines. A wind farm provides a maximum of 1000 MW active power, part of which supplies the HE and the load, and the remaining is injected to a rather weak AC grid with a short-circuit level (SCL) of 2000 MW (equivalent to a short-circuit ratio of 2 considering 1000 MW as base power), and an inertia constant (H) of only 2 s.

Figure 8: Power system configuration under study

The HE system comprises 29 parallel-connected Silyzer 300 modules, yielding a total maximum capacity of 507 MW, with the power load distributed uniformly across all units. Additionally, the response time constant of HE plant (denoted by τ_h and explained in the previous section) is 100 ms, indicating the delay between power reference set-point change and the actual DC current input flow change.

To investigate the ability of the HE plant in providing frequency support for the weak AC grid, two simulation scenarios are considered. (1) Constant-power operation without FSM and voltage-sensitive mode (VSM), which means that the system operates using fixed active and reactive power, and the HE plant would track them regardless of frequency/voltage conditions in the AC grid. (2) Flexible-power operation with FSM and VSM activated, so HE plant adaptively adjusts its power consumption as frequency and voltage conditions in AC grid change. The HE VSC control system is based on the conventional grid-following control with upper-level active and reactive modulation functions as outlined in [63].

The results of the two simulation scenarios are shown in Fig. 9. The wind farm power (P_w) changes via ramp as shown in Fig. 9 a). If the FSM/VSM is disabled on the HE plant, the HE consumes a fixed active power of 420 MW (P_{HE} in Fig. 9 c) assuming HE power setpoint is at 420 MW). As the wind farm power generation reduces, a smaller power is injected into the weak AC network (P_g) since HE plant keeps requesting full power. This gradually causes frequency deviation in AC grid as the overall generation in the network is reduced. However, when FSM/VSM is enabled on the HE plant, the HE power consumption reduces along with the reduction in wind power generation, reducing the frequency stress on the AC grid, and hence, grid frequency deviation becomes smaller. This is the main advantage of the frequency support feature of the HE plant. The impact of VSM on the AC voltage control is shown in Fig. 9 d). As can be seen, the AC voltage has a smaller deviation as HE plant regulates its reactive power (Fig. 9 e)) to fight against voltage variation.

While the activation of FSM/VSM enhances grid stability, it introduces significant fluctuations in hydrogen production (H₂), as illustrated in Fig. 9 f). The reduction of power directly correlates with a lower hydrogen flow rate, subsequently slowing the pressure at storage tanks (Fig. 9 g)). Furthermore, this operational flexibility impacts the thermal

Figure 9: Simulation scenarios 1 and 2, a) wind farm and AC grid active power, b) AC grid frequency, c) active power consumption of HE, d) Terminal AC voltage of HE plant, e) reactive power of HE plant, f) hydrogen mass production rate, g) incremental pressure of hydrogen storage tank, h) efficiency of HE plant, k) electrolyzer stack temperature, and m) electrolyzer stack heat dissipation.

dynamics and heat dissipation of the electrolyzer (Figs. 9 k) and m)). Maintaining the target temperature of 353.15 K becomes challenging when system efficiency drops below 85%, as the resulting high thermal load may exceed the capacity of the current thermal control system. This could be mitigated by considering a higher water flow in the heat exchanger. Conversely, a primary advantage of FSM/VSM activation is the improvement in average electrolyzer efficiency (Fig. 9 h)), as lower operational power levels reduce energy losses, thereby optimizing performance.

However, the dynamic adjustment of BoP components such as heat exchangers, water pumps, and cooling fans, to track power setpoint changes, may impose additional mechanical stress on these assets. Beyond mechanical integrity, the efficacy of frequency support depends on the system's response time. In this study, a time constant of $\tau_h=100$ ms is utilized, characterizing the HE plant as a fast-responding

load. A slower response time would attenuate the reduction in grid frequency deviations, thereby limiting the ancillary service benefits of the FSM.

5. Performance sensitivity to plant response time

In the previous study, the response time constant of the HE plant (τ_h) was assumed to be 100 ms. However, the response time of a such large-scale HE plant might be longer depending on the hydrogen production process constraints and the BoP components dynamics. In this section, the sensitivity of the frequency support performance to a longer HE plant response time is studied. The time constant τ_h is increased from 100 ms step-by-step to maximum 2800 ms.

The frequency dynamics are shown in Fig. 10. Only frequency is plotted to have a better focus on the FSM response.

Figure 10: Sensitivity of frequency support to the HE plant time constant

Figure 11: Sensitivity of frequency support to the HE plant time constant during sudden wind farm power loss, (a) system frequency and (b) electrolyzer power consumption

The bigger τ_h results in a larger frequency deviation, which means the FSM performance is compromised due to the slower BoP response.

It is important to note that the lose of FSM performance is not significant due to slower BoP response, because the wind power varies with a pre-defined ramp rate, commonly specified by the wind turbine manufacturer. In this case study, the wind turbine power ramp rate is assumed 0.25 pu/s (250 MW per second in base power of 1000 MW). Hence, even slower HE plant can still improve the frequency dynamics of the system.

However, if the wind farm power is changed more rapidly with larger magnitude, the lose of FSM performance is more significant. Such situation can happen when wind farm suddenly loses power generation or gets disconnected. Such scenario is also investigated here. The wind farm power goes from nominal to zero at $t = 11$ s. The power reduction is assumed to be as fast as 1 pu per second. The FSM performance is shown in Fig. 11(a), which indicates a major frequency drop once the wind farm power goes to zero. A slower HE plant cannot respond to this change fast enough (see Fig. 11(b)) by rapidly changing its power consumption and therefore counteracting power imbalance.

Similar to any other source of FSM functionality, such as a battery system, the quality of FSM support heavily relies on the response speed of the device and the frequency transient speed. In case of fast frequency transient in the system, a slow device cannot help frequency dynamics via FSM support. The decision to either use HE for FSM functionality should be made only once the speed of frequency transient at the location of installation is studied.

6. Results analysis and discussion

A more realistic representation of the HE system operation is achieved by combining detailed stack models with BoP dynamics. The PEM electrolyzer stack model provides key operational parameters such as temperature, efficiency, and hydrogen generation, across the entire operational range, enabling the selection of optimal working conditions (1 bar and 80°C). Furthermore, incorporating BoP dynamics accurately captures the transient response of the hydrogen plant, which is critical for evaluating the system's capacity to provide grid frequency support.

Building on this framework, the case study evaluates the impacts of constant versus flexible HE power operation on both the electrical grid and the hydrogen plant, with the principal results summarized in Table 5. While operating

Table 5

Comparative analysis of key system parameters during constant versus flexible (FSM/VSM) operation of the HE plant.

Parameter	HE Power Operation	
	Constant	FSM/VSM
Grid		
Wind energy utilization	Suboptimal	Maximized
Grid frequency deviations	↑ Higher	↓ Lower
Reactive power demand	↑ Higher	↓ Lower
HE System		
Applied HE power	Fixed	Variable
Electrolyzer efficiency	Fixed	Variable
Hydrogen generation	Fixed	Variable
Temperature fluctuations	↓ Lower	↑ Higher
Sensitivity to BoP dynamics	↓ Lower	↑ Higher
Operational complexity	↓ Lower	↑ Higher

at a constant power level simplifies tasks such as thermal or storage management and reduces mechanical stress, by maintaining steady hydrogen production, it leads to larger grid frequency and voltage deviations, alongside increased reactive power demands. Furthermore, the intermittency of wind generation complicates constant power operation and to maintain it, the HE plant must either rely on supplementary energy imports during low-wind periods or operate at a reduced baseline capacity, which leads to curtailment during peak generation moments.

Conversely, operating in FSM/VSM mode maximizes wind generation utilization, while also mitigating grid frequency deviations and reactive power requirements. While this strategy enhances grid stability, the power variability introduces fluctuations in the energy supplied to the HE plant. These fluctuations directly impact internal dynamics, including electrolyzer efficiency, thermal management, and hydrogen production. Consequently, the plant experiences greater operational complexity and mechanical stress. Additionally, BoP dynamics are more relevant in FSM/VSM mode, as they influence the system's ability to adapt to new power setpoints.

Given the critical influence of BoP dynamics in flexible power HE operation, this study further analyzed how the plant's response time affects both grid stability and electrolyzer power consumption. The results establish that the system's feasibility for FSM/VSM operation is primarily constrained by two factors: the inherent BoP dynamics and the speed of power generation fluctuations. Specifically, when simulating a wind farm with a power ramp rate of 0.25 pu/s, the results demonstrated that even a hydrogen plant with slow BoP dynamics ($\tau_h = 2800\text{ms}$) can effectively adapt to the power input and improve grid stability. Conversely, when subjected to more abrupt power changes at a rate of 1 pu/s, a slow plant response cannot adapt quickly enough to the transients, thereby causing a power imbalance.

To conclude, this analysis highlights the potential of operating HE plants in FSM/VSM mode. However, choosing between flexible and constant power operation requires a comprehensive, site-specific evaluation. This assessment must account for grid stability, frequency transients, wind power variability, and the time response of the HE system. Furthermore, because the chosen operating mode directly affects hydrogen generation, downstream demand must also be considered to ensure that storage and transport infrastructure can safely accommodate any production fluctuations and satisfy hydrogen supply requirements.

7. Conclusion

This paper presents a hybrid modeling strategy for representing the dynamic behavior of a large-scale PEM water electrolysis plant. The proposed framework combines a physics-based electrolyzer stack model with first-order dynamic representations of balance-of-plant components, including pumps, separators, and heat exchangers. The model was calibrated against the 17.5 MW Silyzer 300 and then scaled to a 507 MW plant using 29 parallel modules, enabling the study of its interaction with a 1000 MW wind power plant, a 100 MW load, and the grid.

The model reproduces the electrolyzer stack performance in agreement with manufacturer data and published references, as reflected in polarization curves and transient responses. It also identifies 80°C and 1 bar as the most efficient operating condition among those evaluated.

Beyond its validation, the model is useful for analyzing how operating strategy affects system-level behavior. In particular, the results show that FSM/VSM control can improve frequency and voltage regulation under wind power variability, although this benefit is accompanied by more variable hydrogen production and a stronger dependence on BoP dynamics. These findings highlight the trade-off between grid-support services and stable hydrogen output.

From a broader perspective, the developed model offers a comprehensive framework for studying large-scale PEMWE plants under dynamic operating conditions. Although its computational cost makes it unsuitable for on-board controllers or high-frequency real-time execution, it is well suited for digital-twin deployment in the cloud, where computational constraints are less restrictive. Coupling this framework with meteorological forecasts and wind-generation predictions could support day-ahead decisions related to storage, transport, and plant scheduling, while also enabling advanced monitoring of operating temperatures, gas generation rates, efficiencies, cooling needs, and storage levels.

Future work will use this framework to evaluate whether selective activation of individual electrolyzer modules improves plant-level efficiency under fluctuating renewable energy inputs.

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